

Tsallis Entropy and Distribution and Function-Inverse Function Pair

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In a previous note (1), we argued that maximizing entropy $-f(e) \ln(f(e))$ or Kaniadakis entropy: $-f(e) K(f(e))$, where K is the Kaniadakis log, subject to the constraints $b_1 f(e)$ (normalization) and $b_2 e f(e)$ (average energy) is equivalent to finding a function $f(e)$ which is the inverse of \ln or K , the Kaniadakis log. In other words, if \ln or K is the inverse of $f(e)$, then $\ln(f(e))=e$ and $K(f(e))=e$ and the entropy becomes $-e f(e)$, the expectation of energy. Thus, one does not really need to go through a maximization process. Recently in the literature (2), a derivation has been given for Tsallis entropy given a power law $f(e)$ i.e. $A e^{-w}$ where w is a constant and e , energy. In this note, we argue this derivation is also based on function-inverse function pairs.

Derivation of Tsallis Entropy in (2)

Ref. (2) presents a power law distribution $f(e)$ which, it is argued, appears frequently in both the social sciences and in nature:

$f(e) = 1/Z (e/T)^{-w}$ ((1)) Here w is a constant and Z a normalization factor. T , a constant, is introduced to represent temperature.

The goal of (2) is to find an entropy function associated with ((1)). It is argued in (2), that this is the Tsallis entropy.

The main procedure used is not to maximize entropy subject to normalization and average energy constraints, but to use the thermodynamic relationship:

$dE = T dS$ where dE is the change in average energy and S the entropy. ((2))

We argue in this note, that ((2)) is already related to function-inverse function pairs. The entropy is usually written as:

$S = -\int de f(e) X(f(e))$ ((3)) where X is usually the natural logarithm, although for the Kaniadakis case, it becomes the Kaniadakis log etc. (Note, the integral is over de if one is using energy levels. In the case of a gas, one usually integrates over dp in one dimension, where p is the momentum, even though one still uses $f(e)$.)

If X and f are inverse pairs, then the entropy ((3)) automatically is of the form of average energy. Thus, it seems one could immediately search for a function X which is the inverse of $f(e)$ given by ((1)). Instead, we first present the argument given in (2).

In (2), the following relationships are stated:

$E = \sum_i e_i p_i(e_i)$ for energy and $S = k \sum_i g_i(p_i(e_i))$ where $g_i(p_i(e_i))$ is an unknown function to be determined.

Next $dE = TdS$ is invoked where $p_i(e)$ becomes $p_i(e) + dp_i(e)$. A fundamental result of (2) is then:

$\sum_i (e_i - g'_i(e_i)kT) dp_i(e) = K \sum_i dp_i = 0$ because $\sum_i dp_i = 0$ (i.e. probability is conserved)

$$g'_i(p_i(e_i)) = 1/T (e_i - K) \quad ((4))$$

((4)) where g' is the derivative of g with respect to $p(e_i)$, is the main equation to be solved. Once one has $g(p(e_i))$, one has the entropy. The authors integrate ((4)) over $dp_i(e)$ (going now from the discrete sum over i to an integral) and use ((1)) to write e_i in terms of $p(e_i)$. The integral is of the form:

$$g(p(e_i)) = \text{entropy density} = \int 1/T(-K) dp_i(e) + 1/T \int e_i dp_i(e) \quad ((5))$$

The first term is a constant because $\int dp_i(e) = 1$ i.e. probability sums to 1.

(It should be noted that in (2), calculations of various normalizations are given, but here we wish only to present the crux of what we think is the main argument.)

It should be noticed that writing e_i (the energy) in terms of $p(e_i)$ involves finding an inverse function of $p(e_i)$ which we call X . Thus:

$$e_i = X(p(e_i)) \quad \text{Here it is } X(p) = p^{-1/w} \quad ((6))$$

Thus, the second integral on the RHS of ((5)) can be performed to yield:

$$1/T \text{ constant } p^{-1/w + 1} / (-1/w + 1) \quad ((7))$$

Thus:

$$g(p) = C_1 + C_2 p^{-1/w + 1} / (-1/w + 1) \quad ((8))$$

which the authors of (2) argue is the form of Tsallis entropy. The authors of (2) go on to calculate C_1 and C_2 .

Inverse Function Argument

We argue the expression for maximization of entropy subject to constraints of normalization and average energy is based on the idea of a function and its inverse. Thus, if one has:

$$f(e) X(f(e)) + b_1 f(e) + b_2 e f(e) \quad ((9))$$

and wishes to find an extremum, an immediate solution is to assign X and f as inverse functions, (b1 introduces a constant which also has to be dealt with, but it usually becomes part of normalization.)

Thus, for the power law case of (2), it is suggested employing the inverse of f(e) and then integrating yields the entropy immediately. Thus:

$$S(e) \text{ the entropy density to be integrated over } de \text{ is of the form } C_1 + C_2 \int df f^{-1/w} = C_1 + C_2 f^{-1/w+1} / (-1/w + 1) \quad ((10))$$

This immediately yields the form of (2) or the Tsallis entropy. (It should be noted that in (2), there are two integrals. The ultimate integral is over de which is usual. The first integral is over dpi because in computing dE=TdS, (2) uses p-> p + dp with Integral dp or Sum dpi =0 as p, the probability, sums to 1.)

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that maximization of entropy subject to an average e constraint or equating dE=T dS are essentially the same process and both have X, f solutions where f(e) is the distribution and X its inverse function. For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, X is the natural log ln and for the Kaniadakis case, the Kaniadakis log. In this note, we try to argue that the same ideas hold for the case of Tsallis entropy (at least following the derivation of (2)). The extra idea in (2) is that in utilizing dE=TdS one introduces the sum or integral of infinitesimal dp where p is probability. Thus, there is an extra dp integral which leads to a form p(e)^q/q (i.e. a q in the denominator).

References

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2. Curado, E., Nobre, F. and Plastino A. Associating an Entropy with Power-Law Frequency Events (Entropy Vol 20 Issue 12, 2018)
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